

**Inductive Verification of Topological Robustness:
Analysis of Disorder Effects on Edge States in the 1D SSH Model
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Abstract

This study investigates the robustness of topological edge states in the one-dimensional Su–Schrieffer–Heeger (SSH) model under the influence of disorder. Random variations in hopping amplitudes were introduced to simulate imperfections in realistic systems. Using Python-based simulations on Google Colab, the eigenvalues and inverse participation ratios (IPR) were computed to analyze the persistence of edge states under different disorder strengths (Δ). The results show that edge states remain robust under weak disorder ($\Delta \leq 0.2$), gradually degrade in intermediate ranges ($\Delta = 0.3–0.5$), and collapse at strong disorder ($\Delta \geq 0.6$). Although limitations such as finite system size and fixed random seed exist, this project demonstrates that inductive simulations can provide valuable insights into the practical robustness of topological systems.

I. Introduction

In the 21st century, physics has entered the era of quantum mechanics, as recognized by multiple Nobel Prizes awarded in 2005, 2012, and 2022 for advances in quantum phenomena and their applications. One of the most promising directions is the study of topological materials, which serve as the foundation for quantum computing and next-generation electronic technologies. Topological insulators are materials that do not conduct electricity in the bulk but allow conduction at their edges due to topological properties. These properties enable robust transport that is immune to certain types of perturbations. This study focuses on the Su–Schrieffer–Heeger (SSH) model, a one-dimensional chain with alternating hopping strengths (v, w), which predicts the existence of localized edge states under specific conditions.

The purpose of this study is to question whether the SSH model can maintain its edge states in the presence of realistic imperfections such as disorder or noise. By introducing random disorder into the hopping amplitudes and analyzing the resulting eigenstates and IPR values, this research seeks to inductively verify the robustness of topological states.

II. Theoretical Background

The SSH model describes a one-dimensional tight-binding chain with alternating intra-cell and inter-cell hopping parameters, v and w . When $w > v$, electrons delocalize toward the edges, forming zero-energy localized edge states. In realistic systems, disorder inevitably arises from irregular atomic positions, phonons, or external interference. Here, disorder is modeled as random variations in v and w , drawn from a uniform distribution within a range $[-\Delta, \Delta]$. The inverse participation ratio (IPR) is used as a measure of localization, where higher IPR indicates stronger edge localization.

$$H = \sum_{n=1}^N (va_n^\dagger b_n + wa_{(n+1)}^\dagger b_n) + h.c.$$

Figure 1. Hamiltonian of the SSH model.

III. Methodology

The SSH Hamiltonian was implemented in Python using NumPy and SciPy. Simulations were performed on Google Colab. The system size was chosen as $N = 20$ unit cells (40 sites). Disorder was introduced by adding random variations within $[-\Delta, \Delta]$ to the hopping amplitudes. Eigenvalues and eigenvectors were computed, and the IPR values were calculated for each eigenstate. Simulations were repeated with Δ ranging from 0.1 to 0.9, with seed fixed at 23. Representative code snippets included functions to construct the Hamiltonian, compute eigenvalues, and calculate IPR.

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from scipy.linalg import eigh

# 1. SSH Hamiltonian generation function
def build_ssh_hamiltonian(N, v, w, delta=0.0, seed=None):
    if seed is not None:
        np.random.seed(seed)

    H = np.zeros((2 * N, 2 * N))

    for n in range(N):
        a = 2 * n
        b = 2 * n + 1

        # Introduction of random defects ([-delta, delta] range)
        dv = np.random.uniform(-delta, delta)
        dw = np.random.uniform(-delta, delta)

        H[a, b] = v + dv
        H[b, a] = v + dv

        if b + 1 < 2 * N:
            H[b, b + 1] = w + dw
            H[b + 1, b] = w + dw

    return H

# 2. IPR calculation function
def compute_ipr(eigenvectors):
    return np.sum(np.abs(eigenvectors)**4, axis=0)

# 3. experimental function
def run_ssh_ipr_simulation(N=20, v=0.6, w=1.4, delta=0.1, seed=23):
    H = build_ssh_hamiltonian(N, v, w, delta, seed)
    eigvals, eigvecs = eigh(H)
```

```

ipr_values = compute_ipr(eigvecs)

# Calculate overall IPR mean value
ipr_mean = np.mean(ipr_values)

# Calculate the mean value of IPR corresponding to eigenvalues with an
energy of -0.25 to 0.25
center_indices = np.where((eigvals >= -0.25) & (eigvals <= 0.25))[0]
center_ipr_values = ipr_values[center_indices]
center_ipr_mean = np.mean(center_ipr_values) if len(center_ipr_values) > 0
else None

# Visualization
plt.figure(figsize=(8, 4))
plt.plot(eigvals, ipr_values, 'o')
plt.xlabel('Energy')
plt.ylabel('IPR')
plt.title(f'SSH Model IPR ( $\Delta = \{\text{delta}\}$ , seed =  $\{\text{seed}\}$ )')
plt.grid(True)
plt.show()

# numerical output
print(f"Overall IPR Mean Value: {ipr_mean:.4f}")
if center_ipr_mean is not None:
    print(f"Average IPR with energy in the range of -0.25 to 0.25:
{center_ipr_mean:.4f}")
else:
    print("Energy does not have an eigenvalue in the range of -0.25 to
0.25.")

return eigvals, ipr_values

# practice
eigvals, ipr_values = run_ssh_ipr_simulation(delta=0.001, seed=23)

```

Figure 2. Example of a Python simulation.

IV. Results

Graphs of eigenvalue vs. IPR for $\Delta = 0.1$ to 0.9 demonstrate a clear transition from robust edge states to their gradual collapse. At low disorder ($\Delta \leq 0.2$), localized edge states appear at zero energy with high IPR. At intermediate disorder ($\Delta = 0.3$ – 0.5), the distinction between bulk and edge states becomes less clear. At strong disorder ($\Delta \geq 0.6$), edge states collapse and bulk-edge separation blurs. Anomalous behavior was observed at $\Delta = 0.9$, likely due to numerical limitations.

Figure 3. Eigenvalue vs IPR at $\Delta = 0.1$

Figure 4. Eigenvalue vs IPR at $\Delta = 0.8$

Δ	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9
Overall IPR Average	0.0682	0.0944	0.1308	0.1702	0.1987	0.2289	0.2464	0.2605	0.2837
IPR average in a range of 0.25,-0.25	0.3567	0.3684	0.3801	0.3915	0.4027	0.4135	0.4234	0.4313	0.3621

Table 1. Average IPR values at different disorder strengths.

V. Discussion

The results support the expectation that SSH edge states are robust only up to a finite disorder strength. The inductive simulation approach proved effective for capturing qualitative behavior but has limitations: the small system size ($N=20$) does not approximate the infinite limit, and the use of a fixed seed prevents statistical averaging. Despite these constraints, the methodology provided useful insight into the robustness of topological states.

Future work could extend this analysis by increasing system size, averaging over multiple disorder realizations, and testing universal scaling hypotheses (such as the single-scale hypothesis).

VI. Conclusion

This study inductively verified the robustness of topological edge states in the one-dimensional SSH model under disorder. Edge states persisted under weak disorder but gradually collapsed at higher levels. While certain limitations remain, the project demonstrates that inductive simulation methods can provide valuable insights into advanced quantum phenomena, even at the high school research level.

Works Cited

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